

Ellen G. White Counsel on Functional Youth Ministry: Implication for Caring for Youth in the Seventh-day Adventist Church, Nigeria

Isaiah Ola Abolarin, PhD

College of Post Graduate Studies/Department of Religious Studies

Babcock University, Ilishan-Remo, Ogun State, Nigeria

abolarini@babcock.edu.ng +2347011213441

ORCID ID: 0000-0002-3276-684X

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Abstract

The mission of the Seventh-day Adventist Church is to announce and prepare people for the second coming of Christ. This task is for both adults and youths to accomplish. Youth attrition from faith is a concern for religious leaders and many have written on different approaches to checkmate the phenomenon. The Seventh-day Adventist Church, especially in Nigeria is gifted with many young people but the church is faced with challenges of keeping the young people in the faith and in getting them engaged. Despite different organizations like pathfinder club and campus ministry, and different activities like youth camp and congresses, the challenges still remain. The functionality of youth ministry can be determined by how the young people are retained and are committed in the faith. The question therefore is, what else could be done to have a functional youth ministry in the Seventh-day Adventist Church in Nigeria? This study explored the counsels from Ellen G. White on youth ministry, extracting principles the church in Nigeria could adopt as part of the necessary overhaul of youth ministry. These will guide towards an intentional and functional youth ministry which will generate active and positive youth engagement in the mission of the church.

Keywords: functional youth ministry, mission of the church, second coming of Christ, youth engagement, young people

Introduction

Considering writings from psychological, educational, and social point of view, different authors have written about the importance of intentionality in caring for the development of young people (Abolarin, 2017; Amero, et al., 2024; James, 1994; Jones & Wilder, 2010; Kim, 2010; Parrot, 2000; Willimon & Naylor, 1995). In addition, scholars from religious and spiritual backgrounds have emphasized the need to work with young people for their spiritual development. They argued that without this kind of approach, young people's attrition from faith will continue to increase (Anderson, 2006; Estep Jr., 2010; Garber, 2007; Kinnaman & Lyons, 2007; Morgenthaler, et.al., 2014; Seymour, 1982; Tippen, 2008; Willoit & Dettori, 1995). These scholars consistently emphasis intentionality in caring for youth spirituality. Westerhoff (2000), specifically addresses the church, calling on the Christian church to be intentional in caring for the holistic development of her young people.

The need for all-round, intentional care for youths is a necessity which can no longer be ignored in the Seventh-day Adventist Church (SDA) especially in Africa and specifically in Nigeria. Interactions with SDA young people from some parts of Nigeria and specifically in classrooms

encounters while teaching those studying to become pastors have revealed that many of the youth are deeply concerned about the undisguised neglect of the young people in the church. They often perceive themselves as being left unengaged and unequipped for the many roles they could play in accomplishing the mission of the church. The prevalent impression among young people seem to be that the church has no genuine interest in the affairs of their lives be it, social, physical, emotional, intellectual or spiritual. Having worked with the young people for many years, their intrinsic need for love, identity, hope, ownership, and participation in the church has become too glaring to be ignored. They have questions and challenges they want the church to respond to or assist them with. As these challenges begin to worsen with the rapid global changes including rapid technological evolution and attendant assaults on faith and morality, the youth naturally become desperate for answers and direction. However, the depth of this desperation seem to be lost on many leaders and adults in the society and the church judging by their lack of interest in matters that concern the youth. This situation served as motivation for the current study in which the paper investigated if there are counsels or principles related to youth life and ministry given by God to His church through Ellen G. White. Ellen G. White was one of the pioneers of the SDA church, a woman of remarkable spiritual gifts. She wrote more than 5,000 periodical articles and 40 books. Her writings covered a broad range of subjects, including religion, nutrition, education, social relationships, evangelism, prophecy and management (White, 2018). Her writings have influenced families, schools, society, and SDA church. She lived most of her life during the 19th century (Kaiser, 2012)

It goes without saying that life in the 21st century and the shape of society with the onslaught of the 4th industrial revolution and advancement in technology cannot be matched with the type of life lived by young people within the period when Ellen G. White wrote her counsel nevertheless, as typical of inspired writings, the paper presumed that there would be some timeless principles which may still be applicable in the current days and situations from her writings.

The paper used desk research adopting traditional method of literature review in which a comprehensive overview of existing research on a specific topic is given. It involves summarizing, analyzing and synthesizing previous studies to highlight trends, debates and gaps. At the beginning of this enquiry, a major concern had to do with the fear that the paper might not get sufficient information needed to address the issue under consideration. This concern was not unrelated to the assumption that the challenges being faced by young people today were not present in Ellen G. White's days therefore she probably did not write anything to address the challenges of today. Another concern of the assumptions is that there was no prominent problem of youth and the church in Ellen G. White days. On commencing the study however, it became clear that her writings contained so many vital information about all aspects of the life of the youth that nearly, the focus of the inquiry of paper would have changed. There were information in the manuscripts that were personal in nature as they were addressed to specific individuals but after careful consideration of such information, it was discovered that though the letters were for specific individuals, the principles were general and have timeless application. Some of these messages were so relevant and timely that it would be a great advantage if they were copied and sent out to be read in local churches all over the world.

Reading through some of the Ellen G. White writings brought about intriguing discoveries on caring for the development of young people in the SDA church. The following are the summaries

of the findings on the counsels and guidelines on the ideal relationship between the church and the young people, especially in this perilous time when the church is to be more committed to her mission of preparing people for the second coming of Jesus Christ.

Understanding the Youth

Considering the important place occupied by the youth in the society, home, and the church, having a good understanding of who they are and what their needs are has an important role to play in leading them aright. To Ellen G. White, youth are important that their lives are to be understood. She wrote concerning different aspects of youth live. Contrary to the view of many people and organizations, Ellen G. White considered youth age to be up to 37 years. This was expressed in her response to Elder Waggoner's letter in regard to his connection with the Berrien Spring School as Bible teacher in 1902 AD. On the first page of the letter Ellen G. White made reference to brother Sutherland's age being "37 years old" as "he is young" (White, 1902a). Although the age of youth in the 21st century, according to the United Nations ranged between 15 and 24 (United Nations, 2015, May), this reduction could be as a need to prioritize limited resources, tackle unemployment and reflect faster developmental transitions in policies that guide the care for the youth. As of 2019, the age of youth in Nigeria was 15—29 (Federal Ministry of Youth and Sports Development, 2019). All these indicated that youth are considered to be important and deserve to be recognized in the society.

Regarding the youth and older Christians, White (1902a) made an important observation that "In some respects, youthful Christians have not so much to battle with as older Christians". Whereas the older ones ought to be guardians to youth, it is disturbing that, in many instances, they could be the battles to the youth. This is also the situation in many Nigerian society as argued by Oluwagbohunmi (2014) and Shuaibu, et al. (2018); and specifically in the SDA church in Nigeria (Efuntade, 2021; Ishaya, 2022). Ellen G. White indeed knew who the youth were and the challenges facing them. The youth, according to her, were living in "these last days of peril and corruption." They were "exposed to many trials and temptations" (White, 1886). This same view was presented in another way by Osmer (2001) in his lecture on youth, church and culture (p. 83); in which he presented globalization as a knitting process bringing the world to a single place through an interconnected system of communication, transportation, political organization, and economic exchange which through media "sweeps" the youth "along in a current far stronger than they are." It "pulls them into the global cultural flows of the entertainment industry." Through these media, according to Osmer (2001), are music, movies, and television which "communicate a view of life that is antithetical to the most cherished values and understanding of Christianity" (Osmer, 2001). In the 21st century, not just media but social media and technological explosion, have swept the youth from the society of value to the one where no value is cherished. The SDA church is not at the same pace with technological advancement in leading and influencing the youth who are being taken over by technological and other trending issue like LGBTQPLUS (Abolarin, 2024). Having to face such large scale complication and confusion, the youth unfortunately compare themselves with others, according to Ellen G. White, "they will say, 'I am as good as that young man Because of so many halfhearted professors, very fun and frolic, jesting, and joking, would not be of any benefit to them, and the subject of religion is presented in an unfavorable light'" (White, 1890a). This comparison brings a concern for the youth of the SDA in Nigeria, especially with the loss of interest in religion (Abolarin, 2015)

The Needs of Youth

Ellen G. White was very much in the knowledge of the needs of the youth. She wrote on their needs at home, school, and church. Before looking into each of the areas of the needs, she brought everything together by saying that “they need an infallible guide, an unerring counselor. This they will find in the Word of God. Unless they are diligent students of that Word, they will make grave mistakes which will mar their own happiness and that of others, not only in the present but in the future life” (White, 1886). In another way, the youth desire authenticity, genuine concern and love and mentoring. This is an important principle for motivating youth positive and holistic development. “A nation that intends to have a prosperous future will guide, build, equip and nurture its young people . . . they are the nation’s future assets” (Abolarin, 2024, p. 77). This section will not deal much with the needs of the youth as Ellen G. White perceived them as these needs are embedded in the other sections.

Interest in Youth

Ellen G. White demonstrated a high degree of interest and concern for the youth. Considering how Satan is destroying them she stated that, “There are young men and women who absorb or receive all Satan’s plans and suggestions and act them out as cunningly and secretly and as perseveringly as Satan himself. They are never content unless they are working for their master to ruin souls” (White, 1888). This paints a terrible picture of the enslavement of the minds of young people by the adversary. In the same letter she declared, “I feel that I can do good missionary work in looking after the young men and women who need help, and bringing them into a position where they will have influence the opposite entirely from that which Satan is exercising.” Still on the same issue she claimed, “I have deep interest in all youth. Is not every youth under a terrible deception, who thinks he has discovered a happier way?” (White, 1890a). Her deep interest and concern for youth is not just by “saying” but also by acting. There was a particular youth meeting in December 1889 that she attended despite that she was ill. She said, “I inquired Monday evening just before the close of the old year if Homer would be at the meeting for the youth . . . last night I was solicited to go to the meeting in the tabernacle for youth although I had sent for the doctor . . . yet my interest was so great for the young. I went to the meeting. We had a very precious meeting. Fifty came forward for prayers . . . God has been sending message of warning, of reproof, of entreaty for the youth to awaken from their sleep and to lift the burdens of Christ and to be obtaining a valuable experience.” Speaking to the youth she said, “I love your soul. I have been deeply interested in you. I want you to be right with God” (White, 1890b). The genuine interest in the youth by E. G. White is an ideal attitude to be demonstrated on the youth in the 21st century SDA church. Goudeau (2015) argued that the bonding between youth and adults is critical to the development of adaptive responses and life skills for functionality of young people. Genuine interest by adults in SDA youth is essential for retention, mentoring and spiritual growth among the youth (The Adventist Youth Ministries Department, 2025).

Youth Self-Perception

It is evident how great interest and concern demonstrated by Ellen G. White toward the youth. She also had a good understanding of how the youth perceive themselves. This is another critical ingredient to a successful youth ministry. Writing about youth’s fascination for fictional writings she said, “I am laboring to call the attention of the young to close searching of the scriptures. Youth are enchanted, infatuated with the false . There is only one remedy; that is to become conversant with the scripture” (White, 1886). She also wrote in the same letter about the hidden

behavior of “youth working in secrecy, acting a part that is not frank and open, and according to the Bible standard. By this course they educate themselves to be untrue to those who love them most, and who are trying to be faithful guardian over them.” With this she called upon the youth to have understanding “of their own weakness” and if they do, “they would go to God for earnest strength” (White, 1895).

The youth are to realize the need of being much in prayer, of being rooted and grounded in the truth, so that by precept and example they might be living witnesses for Christ. According to Ellen G. White, there is “wide sphere of usefulness for youth, but they see it not” (White, 1948a, p. 512). One of the major problems of youth is idleness, just as it has been mentioned, not that there is nothing to do but that they do not see it. In this regard, Ellen G. White wrote, “idleness leads many to evil and degrading practices” (White, 1890, p. 601). Also, she said “idle hands and brains of youth, ready for Satan to control (White, 1948a, p. 395). And God, according to Ellen G. White, “has work for every youth” (White, 1890, p. 574). There is no justification for idleness in the life of youth. They may not see unless they are guided adequately.

God has given strength to the youth to work for the Master. “Young men and women, God calls upon you to work, work with your strength for Him. Make an entire change in your course of action. You can do work that those who minister in words or doctrine cannot do. You can reach a class whom the minister cannot affect” (White, 1948, p. 513). The Lord calls for young men and women to enter His service. “If the youth would place their affections, their strength upon Christ and heaven, doing the will of God, they will have a hope of the better life that is enduring and they will abide forever, being crowned with glory, honor, immortality, eternal life.” (White, 1948, p. 498). The Lord counts much on the youth because “much can be done by them for Christ” (White, 1963, p. 312). And it is a “privilege for youth to be co-worker with angels” (White, 1903, p. 271). The mind and the focus of the youth is usually on something entirely different and Ellen G. White was quite aware of this. She therefore counselled, “The highest aim of our youth should not be to strain after something novel, but to place themselves under the teaching of the Holy Scriptures. Then they may possess the attributes classed as the highest in the heavenly courts” (White, 1897a). The youth are to allow God’s word in them and be devoted to His services, giving all their power to work for Him. By this, they will be able to stand and aspire high. Youth need God, they need the Bible and they need prayer. “The youth should bear in mind that their physical strength, their mental qualification, soul, body and spirit, are to be devoted to service. They are never to be misapplied, never misused and never left to rust from inaction” (White, 1897b). Also, God holds everyone, including the youth, accountable for improving the capabilities and powers that He has given to them. They are to seek to reach the highest standard of efficiency. “This requires that we be much engaged in earnest prayer, that we be shut in with God, holding communion with our Lord Jesus Christ. Our young men and women should be workers devoted to the Mater’s service. If they will walk in the light which the Lord has permitted to shine upon them, they will see precious opportunities which they may improve, and do God’s will from the heart” (White, 1894a). When youth do this, their affections will become pure, refined and sanctified, and they may grow up to the full stature of men and women in Christ Jesus. Youth can have different difficulties even when trying to serve God. To this Ellen G. White wrote, “I would impress upon the youth that Daniel’s God is their God, and whatever difficulty may arise, let them do as did Daniel, ‘seek mercies of the God of heaven’” (White, 1894).

Home Background

Before the youth could live, take decisions and serve God, the home or parents and the church would have contributed to their different developmental stages right from infancy. According to Ellen G. White, “a noble, all-round manhood does not come by chance. It is the result of the molding process of character-building in the early years of youth, and a practice of the law of God in the home. God will bless the faithful efforts of all who teach their children as He has directed” (White, 1986). Are all youth privileged to have such background? Ellen G. White stated, “I feel deeply in regard to those youth who have no advantage of proper instruction in the home, who are not brought up in the fear and love and admonition of the Lord” (White, 1897a). It is important for parents to teach their children obedience to God and His word and to them as parents. Using Elisha as an example of proper up-bringing, Ellen G. White wrote that, Elisha was “trained in habits of simplicity, of obedience to his parents and to God. Integrity and fidelity and the love and fear of God were his” (White, 1897a). It is only those who render perfect and thorough obedience to God that He will choose and this begins in the home. Parent are to be like Abraham who “will command not by any act of violence, but kindly, firmly” to obey God’s commandment. “He will allow no oppression, no filial disobedience.” Abraham would combine influence of decided authority mingled with love, and rule his household in the fear of God. According to Ellen G. White, “there is not greater cruelty than to allow children to control in the home. Parents are not to indulge their natural affection at the expense of truth, duty and righteousness, by putting the line of control in the hands of the child” (White, 1906).

Parents are to faithfully guard the feet of their inexperienced youth and educate and train them to fear and love God, and to serve Him with an undivided heart. The youth are to obey the admonition that comes down to them in the sacred records through the ages to their time that they may be wise in heavenly wisdom (White, 1894b). The up-bringing of youth has much to do with his or her attitude to religion later in life. Ellen G. White stated that if the youth are not properly brought up, they “presume to insinuate doubts concerning the fundamental principles of Christianity . . . they are thus led to jest at the faith of their fathers and to do despite to the Spirit of grace” (White, 1911, p. 60). Speaking on the up-bringing of the Waldenses, Ellen White wrote, “parents’ tender and affectionate as they were, loved their children too wisely to accustom them to self-indulgence . . . They were educated from childhood to endure hardness, to submit to control and yet to think and act for themselves. Very early, they were taught to bear responsibilities, to be guarded in speech, and to understand the wisdom of silence. While the youth were inured to toil and hardship, the culture of the intellect was not neglected. They were taught that all their powers belonged to God and that all were to be improved and developed for His service” (White, 1911, pp. 67, 68). The way the youth are brought up is crucial so they will live their lives in service for God. They are to be carefully, judiciously trained. They are not to be left to grow as they will. They are to be taught to form symmetrical characters that God can approve. They need to be surrounded with wholesome, uplifting influences and the standard set before them must be high. Parents themselves should allow the Spirit of God in them in order to train their children in line with divine expectations. “The fathers and the mothers who are in the church, are under soared obligation to watch for the souls of their children as they must give an account” (White, 1906). Parents are to be called to account, if they do not bring sound doctrine into their home life. “Christianity in the home is a requirement of God. Home education means much. It is a matter of great scope. The father must not betray his sacred trust. He must not, on any point, yield up his parental authority. He is to be the priest and house-band of his home . . .

Neither father nor mother is to permit blind affection to lead them to indulge their children. Every father and mother is answerable to the great law-giver for the children placed in their care” (White, 1897a). Together, parents and children are to walk in the way of the Lord, ruled and guided by His Holy Spirit. The children are not to be indulged, and allowed to think that they can follow their own desires without asking the advice of their parents.

The Role of the Church

Apart from the role of parents in the life of the youth, Ellen G. White has a lot on the relationship between the youth and the church. According to her, there has been altogether too little attention paid to the children and the youth, and they have failed to develop as they should in the Christian life, just because the church members have not looked upon them with tenderness and sympathy, desiring that they might be advanced in the divine life. “In our large churches, very much might be done for the youth” (White, 1896 April). For this reason, the work that lies next to the church members (fathers and mothers) is to become interested in the youth of the church, for the youth need kindness, patience, tenderness, line upon line, precept upon precept. White (1896, April) lamented,

O, where are the fathers in Israel? We ought to have large number of them who would feel not merely a casual interest, but a special interest in the young. We ought to have those whose hearts are touched by the pitiable situation in which our youth are placed, who realized that Satan is working by every conceivable device to draw them into his net. God requires that the church rouse from its lethargy, and see what is the manner of service demanded of them at this time of peril (p. 353).

The church must participate in a practice that presents the gospel to the youth and challenges them to give their life to it. The job of the church members is to help the youth from an inner ideal of what a good person is like not just focusing on the outward. The church has great work to do for and with the youth. Ellen G. White declared, “in the name of the Lord we must call and prepare the young for the battle. They must understand God’s plan for work in every stage of their upward march. They must know for themselves the reason of our faith, and make it their experience” (White, 1897a). The Lord rejoices when young men and women become imbued with His Spirit, and gird on the armor to engage in aggressive warfare. The church is to be the agent through which this will be done. “Youth in their experiences, needed a wise, firm hand to point out the right way and to bar with counsel and restraint the wrong way” (White, 1948b, p. 40). The church members are to exert positive influences upon the youth and help in shaping their “character for the service of God” (White, 1948c, p. 187). Instead of being at logger head with the youth, the ministers have special work to prepare them for service in the church and as missionaries. Ellen G. White said, “the special effort of ministers and of workers all through our ranks for this time should be to turn away the attention of the youth from all exciting stories to the sure word of prophecy” (White, 1948b, p. 519). The ministers and workers “are to devise plans whereby young men and women may be trained to put to use their entrusted talents (White, 1948d, p. 435). The ministers are to do everything to make this happen. Much can be achieved by the church through the youth; as Ellen G. White said, “I saw that many souls might be saved if the young were where they ought to be, devoted to God and to the truth. Those who are working today are to be replaced tomorrow when they cannot do any more.” She continued, “God will call the youth to fill up the places made vacant by death and apostasies” (White, 1897a). Therefore, it is important now to teach them to engage in the activities of the church, “to love

and minister to persons” (Tutsch, nd., p. 344). To encourage them to get engaged in the mission of the church, “youth need the honest expression of feelings that is found in the experiences of mutuality and the challenge of God’s call to everyman” (White, 1930, p. 99). “The Lord will have a well-trained army, ready to be called into action at a word” (White, 1898 March). The youth are to be taught to be workers, and on how to present the third angel’s message to the people (White, 1908). Religion is to be made relevant to youth. According to Ellen G. White, “Religion should not be made to appear gloomy and unattractive, something calculated to detract from (youth’s) happiness, making life tasteless and unenjoyable. Religion was never designed to make one pleasure-less. What can be productive of greater happiness than to enjoy the peace of Christ, the brightness sunshine of His presence?” (White, 1890). The focus of the church members, workers and ministers is to train and bring youth to serve the Lord.

To Ellen G. White, the youth are to play prominent roles in the church and gospel proclamation. Both parents and the church are to work together, making their affairs and nurture a matter of high priority by setting up a system of ministry that truly works, producing young people who have personally encountered the Savior and are committed to His service.

Summary and Conclusion

The major ideas derived from Ellen G. White writings regarding the care for young people include:

1. That “the special effort of ministers and of workers all through our ranks for this time should be to turn away the attention of the youth from all exciting stories to the sure word of prophecy” (White, 1948b, p. 519). The view that caring for youth should be the duty of youth leaders has been put right as the duty of ministers and workers.
2. The call to all members to be involved in the youth work gives a clear direction and if the counsel is heeded, the future of the youth and the church is bright.
3. The youth are not to be ignored but to “share in the labor and responsibility”. The youth are to work as ministers and be involved in the missionary work. According to Ellen G. White, “As we see God raising up young men for his work, we rejoice to see them increasing in the fear of the Lord in proportion as they increase in the knowledge of the truth” (White, 1902b).
4. Having become aware of the high standard of spirituality and service which God has set before the youth as revealed by the counsels of E.G. White explored in preceding sections, pastors, church leaders as well as those involved in youth ministry have consequently received a clear instruction regarding their own responsibility of devising plans whereby young men and women may be trained and supported in order for them to reach this attainable standard.

Although the word intentional was not used by Ellen G. White when it comes to caring for the young people, it is obvious that she was calling the church and parents to be intentional and to give all that is needed in doing this. Having gone through Ellen G. White writings on the issue of caring for young people, one is tempted to think that she lives in this age, witnessing the current situation of things in the church and at home. The timelessness of the messages is outstanding and brings a conviction that she was inspired by God who is Omniscience.

With these messages at the disposal of the church, there is no excuse for the current perfunctory approach to youth ministry in which countless programs are being organized and attended but the lives of majority of the youth remain untransformed. Through the ministry of Ellen G. White, God has equipped the church for adequate ministry to young people until the second coming of Jesus Christ. As important as these messages are to the church, the questions that need to be answered are, 1) Are these messages made available to church leaders, pastors and adults? If they are made available, then, 2) are they accessible to all the stakeholders (leaders, pastors, adults) in the church? 3) Are these categories of people utilizing the messages?

There is a possibility, just as it was with me before going into the search, that leaders, pastors and adults in the church are not even aware of the existence of these messages. There is an urgent need to call the attention of those involved in youth ministry to a fresh interest in and study of Ellen G. White writings especially at this difficult time in history when the lives and destinies of young people are faced with great and unprecedented perils. Departments devoted to youth ministry in the missions and conferences ought to demonstrate a level of commitment that can match and surpass that with which the forces of darkness allure the youth of this generation. Ministers working in this department could liaise with Ellen G. White Estate in their territory to create a handy compilation of the counsel of Ellen G. White on youth ministry which will be made available both in soft and hard copies.

The Lord who knows and holds the future has prepared the church for the future. The urgency and burden of ministering to the youth require a devotion and earnestness that cannot possibly be given by part-time youth directors whose interests lie elsewhere or administrative youth leaders who are not passionate and visionary. Caring for the youth should be a priority to church leaders and pastors because this group of people have the strength, courage, wisdom, means, and connection that adults do not have but which are necessary for accomplishing the mission of the church. The young people are the engine for the church. They are the present and the future of the church. They are to be ahead of their peers and be instrument of connecting their peers to Jesus. We had better not forget the advice, counsels and teaching given to the church by God through his servant Ellen G. White in leading, equipping and engaging the youth for the Lord's business of preparing people for the second coming of Jesus Christ. Understanding the counsels will help church leaders, pastors, and adults in the Seventh-day Adventist Church to have a proper understanding of who the young people are and their position in the church. Also, it will help correct wrong and inimical cultural notions about adult/youth relationship, especially in Nigeria. Following these counsels and being intentional about it will plant the feet of the young people on the path that God desires them to walk in and they will be instruments in His hands to bring people into His kingdom.

References

- Abolarin, I. O. (2015). *Building Student Spirituality: Duty of University Personnel*. Germany: LAP LAMBERT Academic Publishing.
- Abolarin, I. O. (2017). Adolescents' violence: Causes, control and prevention. *Babcock University journal of education*, 3(1&2), 59-74.

- Abolarin, I. O. (2024). Adolescents and religiosity in the age of entertainment. In R. A. Aderanti, & A. M. Gesinde (Eds.), *Contemporary issues on adolescents and counseling* (pp. 71-96). Peter Lang.
- Abolarin, I. O. (2024). Divine mandate in Genesis 1:27 and LGBTQPLUS: Roles of pastoral counsellors. *The Pastoral Counsellors: Journal of Nigerian Association of Pastoral Counsellors*, 3, 1-9.
- Amero, H., Barrow, T., Currie, C., Pochynok, K., Turner, B., Stiller, R., & Bellefeuille, G. (2024). Intentional child and youth care life-space practice: A qualitative course-based inquiry. *American Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences Research (AJHSSR)*, 8(3), 191-196. Retrieved from www.ajhssr.com
- Efuntade, O. (2021, March). Seventh-day Adventist youths and political apathy in Southwest Nigeria: An empirical survey. *Global Journal of Education, Humanities and Management Sciences (GOJEHMS)*, 3(1), 36-48.
- Estep Jr., J. R. (2010). Moral development and Christian formation. In J. R. Estep, & J. H. Kim (Eds.), *Christian formation: Integrating theology & human development* (pp. 123-159). Nashville, TN, USA: B & H Academic.
- Federal Ministry of Youth and Sports Development. (2019). *Federal Republic of Nigeria National Youth Policy: Enhancing youth development and participation in the context of sustainable development*. Federal Ministry of Youth and Sports Development.
- Goudeau, S. M. (2015). *Principal motives of positive youth-adult relationships: A model for identifying the motives of adult volunteers and youth-adult relationships in physical activity-based youth development programs*. A dissertation submitted to the Graduate Faculty of the Louisiana State University and Agricultural and Mechanical College in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of Doctor of Philosophy in the School of Kinesiology.
- Ishaya, I. (2022, September). Mentoring youth for mission in the twenty-first (21st) century: A case study of the Seventh-day Adventist Church, Nigeria. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science (IJRISS)*, VI(IX), 190-199.
- James, M. H. (1994). *Social problems*. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice Hall.
- Jones, T. P. & Wilder, M. S. (2010). Faith development and Christian formation. In J. R. Estep, *Christian formation: Integrating theology and development* (pp. 161-207). Nashville, TN: B & H Academic.
- Kaiser, D. (2012). *Ellen G. White's life of Christ: An episode in the history of early Adventist translation work*. Digital Commons @ Andrews University. Retrieved from <https://digitalcommons.andrews.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1025&context=church-history-pubs>
- Kim, J. H. (2010). Intellectual development and Christian formation. In J. R. Estep, *Christian formation: Integrating theology and human development* (pp. 63-97). Nashville, TN: B & H Academic.
- Kinnaman, D., & Lyons, G. (2007). *Un-Christian: What a new generation really thinks about Christianity . . . and why it matters*. Grand Rapids, MI, USA: Baker Books.

- Oluwagbohunmi, M. F. (2014, April). An overview of the challenges facing youths in Nigerian society. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 4(6), 154-161.
- Osmer, R. R. (2001). A checklist for the journey: Biblical foundations of ministry with youth. *Princeton Forum on Youth Ministry*. The Institute for Youth Ministry, Princeton Theological Seminary.
- Parrott III, L. (2000). *Helping the struggling adolescent*. Grand Rapids: Zondervan.
- Seymour, J. L. (1982). Approches to Christian education. In J. L. Seymour, *Contemporary approaches to Christian education* (pp. 11-34). Nashville, TN: Abingdon Press.
- Shuaibu, H., Ahmed, S., Suleiman, R. A., Rabe, J. M., & Abdulmumini, L. (2018, June). Socio-economic challenges and prospects of youths in Nigeria. *Zaria Sociological Journal*, 5(2), 163_170.
- The Adventist Youth Ministries Department. (2025). *Pastors and elders handbook: For Adventist Youth Ministries*. The General Conference of Seventh-day Adventists.
- Tutsch, C. (nd). The development of Adventist youth groups and Ellen White's empowerment of youth in evangelism and service. *Ministering with Millennials*, 173-177.
- United Nations. (2015, May). Youth population trends and sustainable development. *Population Facts*. Retrieved from <https://www.un.org/esa/socdev/documents/youth/factsheets/YouthPOP.pdf>
- White, A. L. (2018). *Ellen G. White: A brief biography*. Ellen G. White Estate, Inc.
- White, E. G. (1886). Ellen G. White visit to Nimes, France, Ocotber 16-31, 1886. *Manuscript Release*, 3(162-209).